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Capacity Building Training Needs Of Lecturers Of Business Education For Instructional Delivery In Colleges Of Education In Adamawa And Taraba States, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the capacity building training needs for business education lectures for instructional delivery. In this study, a survey research design was adopted for the collection of data. It adopted a structured questionnaire of 71 participants of Lectures and technologies of the colleges in Adamawa and Taraba states, Nigeria. The survey study encompassed two higher instructions for the research that was conducted; College of Education, Hong and Zing College of Education all in Adamawa and Taraba States. The population of the study was divided into two groups, the lecturers and the instructors. The instrument for the collection of data was the Capacity Building Training Needs Questionnaire (CBTNQ) consists of 54 capacity-building items. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Part one comprises the demographic data of the respondents and part two is subdivided into six sections; instructional planning, instructional organization, instructional implementation, class management, instructional materials, and instructional evaluation. This four-point response scale (4, 3, 2, 1) was used by lecturers and instructors. T-test analysis was analyzed to show the difference between the two groups. It evaluated the statistical calculation to test this study's hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The objective of this study investigation shows there's no significant difference in instructional planning, organization, implementation, class management, materials, and evaluation. This study ascertains the capacity-building training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in educational institutions in Adamawa and Taraba states. This study concluded with an actionable recommendation for educators, instructors, policymakers, and stakeholders to enhance effective teaching in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba states for profound business education through inclusive capacity-building initiatives.

Keywords: Capacity-building, Business Education, Training, Instructions, Delivery, Institutions.

INTRODUCTION

Education is a systematic instruction that involves the process of learning and acquiring knowledge and skills. According to Melaiye et al (2021) on education, education is a key discipline in any society that serves as the foundation for knowledge acquisition, skills improvement, and technological advancement. It is an indispensable sector in any country. Education cultivates an individual capacity and ability, such as physical, intellectual, social, and emotional. The individual's potential enables the improvement of the educational system. Stating that education is essential for individuals and society for better living is

regarded as long-term productivity for an individual and society. Thus, education with effective instructions develops human capital as well as adds moral and mental values to students (Melaiye et al, 2020). A need for effective teaching enhances the learning process as it results in implementing the policy, planning, and organizing the instructional requirements for performance expectations. However, are effective teaching prominent in the school and society? Educators, instructors, community members, and policymakers are required to collaborate to implement effective teaching. Students differ in learning, and teachers encounter different students. It's the advancement of learning that creates effective teaching irrespective of their differences. Hence, teaching components are enhanced to broaden the methodologies on an annual basis. Integrating diverse strategies and new technologies into the curriculum will foster effective teaching. This fosters creativity and innovation by implementing diverse methodologies of these essential components of effective teaching (American Council on Education, 2018).

The components of education are theoretical and practical. Courses in various fields have different techniques for effective teaching. However, business education courses use practical methods to improve student learning experiences.

Business Education is a branch of education that focuses on the imparting of knowledge, the acquisition of skills, and the operation of the business industry. These components are pertinent and marketable to students, which helps them operate efficiently in the professional system. Business education is an inclusive education program that trains an individual to develop fundamental skills necessary for one's future success, office occupation, business industry, economic growth, and entrepreneurship (Onajite, 2016). In Business education, there are diverse teaching methods to facilitate the learning process for students, such as case studies, problem-based learning, industry visitation, presentations, project research, workshops, and seminars. In consideration, these activities have supported the teaching methodologies in the theoretical and practical sense. It provides a comprehensive understanding to facilitate effective teachings of business education to students about vocational practices, management, entrepreneurship, career development, and business. According to Mohommad (2015), the Problem-based learning method allows teachers to help students stimulate their reasoning, acquire knowledge, and collaborate in providing solutions. He stated industry visitation as a method to facilitate students' understanding of diverse organizations on their sustainability and sharing experiences in the career field with their teachers or instructors accompanying them. He also started project research as a potential method for engaging students beyond the classroom and fostering the practical of studying business evolution. Workshops and seminars conducted by experts, teachers, and instructors are imperative for all students. It boosts their confidence and improves their engagement with business orientation.

A teacher is an educator, instructor, or trainer responsible for helping students acquire competence, knowledge, and skills. Who is a business teacher? A business teacher Is a professional, trainer, instructor, teacher, or lecturer who teaches an individual, student, or people by imparting business programs to those interested in the business world. A business educator is a person who deliberately manages the teaching and learning activities of business programs to facilitate a comprehensive understanding that enables individuals to achieve their learning objectives (Agbonaye and Akele, 2017). It could be diverse acquired knowledge or apprenticeship skills involving creativity and innovation. The world evolves in technological advancement. Teachers are lecturers. Lecturers possess a higher certificate like a master's or PhD that allows them to teach, instruct, conduct research, train, and publish scholarly journals. Hence, business lecturers are teachers who teach a particular subject through an innovative approach and structural manner by their academic foundation.

A Business education lecturer enhances effective teaching and learning activities that facilitate students in their capacity and professional in the business world. They improve student academic performance using diverse methodologies to effect changes in students. Their role provides the necessary tools and resources to equip their students. According to the Summit Report 2016, for effective learning outcomes in this modern world, students need educators with comprehensive knowledge and skills to improve their understanding and engagement in a collaborative e-learning environment. It makes an educator follow the trends and themes as the world evolves, where students are enabled to participate and learn more. Either virtual or physical learning, the implementation of teaching activities would be effective and result in

expectations of student academic outcomes and transform the business education courses (Ganyaupfu, 2015). A business education lecturer emphasizes instructional materials and tools to facilitate this teaching to build student capacity. They develop students with a curriculum designed to assist the students in learning. To impart knowledge and skills and evaluate the student learning process. It helps to determine areas for improvement of students and lecturers. Considering the objective of the lesson is achieved. Formative and Summative assessments to build student capacity in their field of learning when necessary. Capacity building is an improvement in a person. It's the process of developing an individual, group, institution, organization, or society to improve their knowledge, skills, and resources to change their performance, solve problems, function, comprehend, and achieve the objective (UNESCO, 2015). It can be regarded as a set of actions intended to foster the participants into understanding and developing their knowledge and skills. Capacity building deals with the necessary attitude to effectively change a person and develop the knowledge, resources, and skills to enhance productivity. Olaiten et al., (2018) stated that capacity building is not only based on knowledge and skills an individual experiences but encompasses the values, tendencies, and attitudes that influence an individual on how they approach specific tasks or how they work in an occupation to achieve proficiency. In business education lecturers, capacity building is essential as it provides training to lecturers, and equips them with teaching strategies and techniques to become more effective and enhance their ability to teach their subject competently (Business Education) and inspire students. However, it's crucial to identify the gaps between their competence and needs. It analyses the lecture skills and the needed skills for effective teaching. It focuses more on planning, organizing, implementing, and achieving lesson objectives. It fosters the appropriate behavior and attitudes toward their teaching roles. A Business educator lecturer expands their roles by integrating diverse development, including leadership, technology, learning methodology, entrepreneurial competencies, and the business world.

Statement of the problem

Several studies have been conducted on teachers' capacity. Lucky and Adebajo (2021) reviewed the effectiveness of teachers' capacity-building using a descriptive survey design of 300 respondents through purposive sampling. The study shows the significance of capacity building on the impact of human development. It analyses the various challenges that obstruct teachers' capacity-building in Nigeria. The study also illustrated recommendations on diverse strategies to improve effective learning through teachers' building capacity. Ikeanyiowu and Enwere (2020) investigated business education teachers on key competencies essential for 21st-century skills. The research was conducted at two colleges of education in the eastern part of Nigeria, known as Anambra State. A descriptive survey design was conducted by 45 business education lecturers with 31-item questionnaires. The analyzed t-test level of significance was 0.05. The resulting finding and conclusion showed that business education lecturers' e-learning facilities in teaching and learning. The study recommends the influence of sufficient training and the use of ICT for effective teaching and learning.

According to Obayi et al., (2020), the success of capacity-building business education lecturers as a discipline is dependent on the number of graduates produced to be independent or not, whether they are to adaptable to the workforce, and have a high competitive globally. Hence, to identify these gaps in the capacity-building needs of business education lecturers, and instructors in Adamawa as Taraba states, Nigeria. This study focuses on facilitating effective teaching to prepare students and contribute to the business world and the education system.

Purpose of the Study

1. Determine the planning instruction capacity training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba States, Nigeria.
2. Determine the instructional materials capacity training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba States, Nigeria.
3. Ascertain the assessment of capacity training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba States, Nigeria

Research Questions

1. What are the planning instructions capacity training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba states, Nigeria?
2. What are the instructional material management training needs of business education lecturers for instructional delivery in the colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba States, Nigeria?
3. What are assessment capacity training needs of business education lectures for instructional delivery in the colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba States, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was tested

- 1) There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business education lecturers and instructors in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba states on planning instruction capacity training needs for instructional delivery in the states.
- 2) There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business education lecturers and instructors in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba on instructional materials management training needs for instructional delivery.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the mean responses of business education lecturers and instructors in colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba on assessment capacity training needs for instructional delivery.

METHODOLOGY

The research design used for this study is a survey research design. The population of this study consists of business education lecturers and instructors in Adamawa and Taraba States. The population sample is 71.

The study population was 71 and the representative sample population was 71. The survey included the entire population. Sampling was not used due to its manageable size.

These study instruments and materials include The Capacity Building Needs Questionnaire (CBNQ). The questionnaires consist of 54 capacity-building items. It was divided into two sections, demographic and six components section addressing instructional planning, instructional organization, instructional implementation, classroom management, instructional materials, and instructional evaluation. The four-point response scale ranges from Highly Needed (4), Average Needed (3), Slightly Needed (2), and Not Needed (1) respectively. The respondents were lecturers and instructors in Adamawa and Taraba states.

Copies the questionnaire were distributed to respondents with the help of three assistants. The research assistants followed the guidelines and accurately distributed them to the college of education, business education lectures, and instructors of colleges of education in Adamawa and Taraba states. The local government and schools where researches were conducted were properly identified. The distribution and retrieval process spanned two days.

Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The decision was based on a mean score of 2.50 which determines the baseline for assessing capacity-building. The four-point response scale was calculated. The null hypotheses were tested using t-tests at a 0.05 significant level. The null hypothesis was rejected when the calculated t-value was more than the t-critical value at 0.05 and the null hypothesis was accepted when the t-value calculated was lower than the t-critical value at 0.05.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Testing of Hypothesis

From the data collected, Hypothesis One postulated that “Business lecturers and instructors on capacity-building training needs for instructional planning in Adamawa and Taraba states” was tested using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions with a t-test that tested the level of significance set at 0.05 to test the hypothesis. The result in the table below

Hypothesis one

Hypothesis one postulated that “Business education lecturers and instructors regarding the capacity building training needs required for classroom management in Adamawa and Taraba states.” was tested using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions with a t-test that tested the level of significance set at 0.05 to test the hypothesis. The result in the table below

Table 1: t-test analysis of mean response of Business education lecturers and instructors regarding the capacity building required for classroom management in Adamawa and Taraba states.

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	Df	T	P-value	Decision
Lecturers	50	3.86	.076	.000	69	.000	1.000	Rejected
Instructors	21	3.86						
Total	71	7.72						

From the above table, it shows there is no significant difference regarding the variables. The means for classroom management in building capacity shows the t-test value at (.000) while the p-value at (1.000) is greater than 0.05 significant value. It analyses that there’s no different opinion on capacity building for classroom management for both lecturers and instructors. The null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis two

Hypothesis two postulated that “Business education lecturers and instructors regarding the capacity building required instructional materials in Adamawa and Taraba States.” was tested using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions with a t-test that tested the level of significance set at 0.05 to test the hypothesis. The result in the table below

Table 2: t-test analysis of mean response of business education lecturers and instructors regarding the capacity building required instructional materials in Adamawa and Taraba States.

Categories	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	Df	T	Pvalue	Decision
Lecturers	50	4.01	.061	.009	69	.645	.521	Rejected
Instructors	21	4.00	.000					
Total	71	8.01						

The variables from the above table have no significance. The means for instructional materials in building capacity shows the t-test value at (.045) while the p-value at (.521) > 0.05 significant value. The result indicated an equal opinion on capacity building for instructional implementation for both lecturers and instructors. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis three

Hypothesis three postulated that “Lecturers and instructors of education programs regarding capacity building necessary for instructional evaluations in Adamawa and Taraba states.” were tested using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions with a t-test that tested the level of significance set at 0.05 to test the hypothesis. The result in the table below

Table 3: t-test analysis of mean response of Lecturers and instructors of education programs regarding capacity building necessary for instructional evaluations in Adamawa and Taraba states

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Difference	df	T	P-value	Decision
Lecturers	50	3.7575	.06874	.00750	69	.498	.620	Rejected
Instructors	21	3.7500						
Total	71	7.508						

The variables from the above table have no significance. The means for instructional materials in building capacity shows the t-test value at (.498) while the p-value at (.620) > 0.05 significant value. The result indicated both agree on capacity building for instructional evaluation for both lecturers and instructors. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The value calculated for all six hypotheses shows the reason for their rejection. The p-value is > 0.05 level of significance. It indicates the equality consideration opinion of the business educator lecturers and instructors in Adamawa and Taraba states. A common ground that accepts the need for capacity building in instruction planning, instructional organizing, instructional implementation, classroom management, instructional Materials, and instructional evaluation is necessary to impact effective teaching and learning. The results analyze the need for intervention to address these gaps and develop areas to improve business education programs in the zone.

The result analyzes the effectiveness of planning. It agrees that lecturers and instructors should be equipped to design a comprehensive lesson note that aligns with key objectives for student learning abilities and capacity. According to Olaitan and Ali (2017), this study aligns with the need to plan lesson notes according to the curriculum expectations. This study coincides with that effective planning enhances optimal learning outcomes.

Instructional organizing is effective in teaching and learning to ensure clarity and effective time allocation. This study aligns with Watt (2015), who highlighted the values of the structural manner of instructional organization toward logical sequencing in learning objectives.

This study affirms the utilization of instructible implementation of diverse teaching methodologies. It fosters the student’s understanding with clear instructions. It indicates the significance of the student-centered method, adaptability, and assessment. The role of diverse methodology is to enhance student engagement and comprehension Wilen(2015).

Edward and Ebert (2015) highlighted the gaps in classroom management. Classroom Management enhances the skills for maintaining a positive learning environment, attitudes, and discipline. It shows the dynamics of promoting learning and proactive strategies to foster student engagement and understanding.

The utilization of instructional materials was deduced in this study to emphasize the role. Proper use of material to teach students will facilitate engagement, critical thinking, self-confidence, and retention of concepts. This study also aligns with Amadioha (2009) on the instruction materials in enriching the student learning process.

Lastly, this research aligns with Ekele (2019) on the development of an assessment to measure the learning process of students. The continuous improvement of the teaching and learning strategies will increase diverse instructional methods.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The previous studies on effective teaching and learning identified the need for continuous professional development to enhance learning expectations. Essien (2021) and Olaitan et al. (2018) indicated that lecturers and instructors often lack the skills to incorporate trending teaching strategies and technologies into their instructional practices. There's a high demand for capacity-building in classroom management, and instructional implementation should be consistent (Obayi et al., 2020). Furthermore, it highlighted the barriers, such as instructional materials and reliance on the traditional method that affect teaching and learning outcomes in the region.

The three critical areas are instructional planning, instructional, classroom management, and instructional evaluation were identified. It identifies the gaps in the approaches to foster capacity building in educators. This study concluded that the development of educators on competencies and learning outcomes will produce competent and self-reliant graduates, which will build the business world and future economics of the country.

Based on the findings of this study, it's recommended that integrating institutional professionals collaborate with stakeholders to develop programs and implement diverse capacity-building programs. The integration of modern technology in the institution with the necessary training for educators to enhance effective teaching practice. Furthermore, the provision of adequate resources and government policies will enhance the curriculum objective. Also, Emphasis on programs and the establishment of seminars and workshops will enhance learning outcomes. Lastly, a need for periodic assessment will tailor the requirements and needs of the student.

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